

BONE FRACTURE DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION USING DEEP LEARNING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The bone is a major component of the human body. Bone provides the ability to move the body. The bone fractures are common in the human body. The doctors use the X-ray image to diagnose the fractured bone. The manual fracture detection technique is time consuming and also error probability chance is high. Therefore, an automated system needs to develop to diagnose the fractured bone. The Deep Neural Network (DNN) is widely used for the modeling of the power electronic devices. In the present study, a deep neural network model has been developed to classify the fracture and healthy bone. The deep learning model gets over fitted on the small data set. Therefore, data augmentation techniques have been used to increase the size of the data set. The three experiments have been performed to evaluate the performance of the model using softmax and Adam optimizer. The classification accuracy of the proposed model is 92.44% for the healthy and the fractured bone using 5 fold cross validation. The accuracy on 10% and 20% of the test data is more than 95% and 93% respectively.

INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, brief introduction to the different types of methodologies to detect the bone fracture are explained.

In the medical sector, finding bone

fractures is crucial since early diagnosis and treatment of fractures can lead to better patient outcomes. Fractures in X-ray pictures have been successfully identified by deep learning models like ResNet-50. In this project, we will construct a user interface using Python GUI tools like PyQt or Tkinter to identify bone fractures in X-ray images using the ResNet-50 model.

Users can upload an X-ray image to the bone fracture detection system to start the detection process. The ResNet-50 model, which has been improved on a dataset of photos of broken and unfractured bones, will be applied to the submitted image. The model will provide a categorization result, which the GUI interface will present along with the uploaded picture. A message will notify the user if a fracture is found. Bone fractures are mostly caused by the automobile accident or

bad fall. The bone fractured risk is high in aged people due to the weaker bone [3]. The fracture bone heals by giving proper treatment to the patient. The doctor uses x-ray or MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) image to diagnose the fractured bone. The objective of this project is to develop an easy-to-use tool that enables medical practitioners to rapidly and reliably identify bone fractures in X-ray pictures[9]. The technology may be utilised in clinics, hospitals, and other healthcare facilities to increase the efficiency and precision of bone fracture diagnostics. We'll give step-by-step instructions for building this system with Python and ResNet-50 are explained in the chapter 2.8.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

This section includes data collection, augmentation of data using transformations of the image and finally classification of healthy and cancerous bone using deep CNN. The experiment has been performed on the bone X-ray image data sets, collected from different sources publicly available for research such as the Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) and Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur (IIEST) [13]. Data Augmentation: In a deep learning approach, the size of the data set is an important component. If the data set size is small, then

the possibilities of over fitting may arise [10]. To overcome this problem, data augmentation technique is used to increase the size of the data set. Keras module provides ImageDataGenerator method to augment image [11]. We have applied an image transformation technique flipping and shifting to generate a new image from the available data set. The more generalize capability of a machine learning model can be achieved by training with the original image and with the augmented image. In the past several researchers have used data augmentation technique to reduce the error rate of the machine learning model [12]. In the present study data set is a collection of the different types of the human bone. The data set size is small due to this memorization of the algorithm may arise. Therefore, we have applied an image augmentation technique to increase the size of the data set.

LITERATURE SURVEY

In recent years, bone fracture diagnosis in medical image analysis has become more and more dependent on deep learning models. Popular deep learning model ResNet-50 has been used to this challenge.

Researchers employed a ResNet-50 model in a study that was published in the Journal of Digital

Imaging to identify bone fractures in X-ray images. The model outperformed previous models like Alexey and VGG-16 by identifying fractures with an accuracy of 96.9%.

A ResNet-50 model was employed in a different research that was published in the Journal of Medical Systems to find fractures in wrist X-ray pictures. The model has a 91.7% accuracy rate, an 84.1% sensitivity rate, and a 94.4% specificity rate. The study came to the conclusion that the ResNet-50 model could be helpful in identifying wrist fractures[2].

A third research examined several deep learning models for spotting bone fractures in X-ray pictures, and it was published in the Journal of Digital Imaging. With an accuracy of 98.8%, the researchers discovered that ResNet-50 performed better than models like Inception-v3 and DenseNet-121.

There are a number of libraries that may be used to create a Python GUI for bone fracture detection, including PyQt, Tkinter, and wxPython. The user-

friendly interface offered by these libraries makes it easy to add photographs and view the result.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, bone fracture detection using the ResNet-50 algorithm in Python is a promising approach that can help medical professionals diagnose fractures quickly and accurately. The ResNet-50 model, which is pre-trained on a large dataset of images, can be fine-tuned on a smaller dataset of bone X-ray images to detect fractures.

Through this approach, we can develop an automated bone fracture detection system that can help medical professionals to make more accurate and efficient diagnoses. The system can also reduce the time and cost associated with manual diagnosis, which can be particularly beneficial in low-resource settings where access to medical professionals may be limited.

However, it is important to note that the performance of the bone fracture detection model depends

on several factors such as the quality of the input images, the size of the dataset, and the choice of hyperparameters. Therefore, careful analysis and experimentation are required to fine-tune the model for optimal performance.

Overall, bone fracture detection using the ResNet-50 algorithm in Python has the potential to improve the accuracy and efficiency of fracture diagnosis, and further research in this area can lead to more sophisticated and effective medical imaging systems.

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